

Child labor and its Impact on the Attitude of Child: A Case Study of Sindh

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Abstract:

The current research investigates the Child labor and its Impact on the Attitude of Child: A Case Study of Sindh. Data were collected from 100 respondents from Hyderabad and their vicinity. Stuructural questionnaire was developed for the reliability and valiidity of data. It was revealed that Child labour has negative impact on the attitude of the child. Most of the cases we found that they wont have any interest in labor job but due to poor economic conditions of their families they are forced to do job.

INTRODUCTION:

It is likely that individuals in this study have unobserved attributes (e.g. ability, ambition, etc.) that affect both their schooling and work choices and their adult earnings. Thus any attempt to estimate the effect of working early in life or attaining more schooling on adult earnings will be biased if this source of endogeneity is not properly addressed. Estimates that do not attempt to address this issue are considered unreliable (Becker and Chiswick, 1966; Chiswick, 1974; Mincer, 1974). Much of the recent research into this relationship using US data has relied on the use of instrumental variables to overcome the confounding effects of these unobserved attributes (Cameron and Taber, 2004; Carneiro and Heckman, 2002; Card, 2001; Card, 1995a; Card, 1995b). The main drawback of this type of approach in this case is that it demands a robust set of instruments for the schooling and child labor choices of an individual. The historical data on the availability and quality of educational opportunities as well as proxies for local labor market conditions when an individual was a child allows such an approach to be followed. These institutional variables provide exogenous (to the individual household) variation in the cost and benefits of going to 4 school and working and are therefore very likely to be correlated with the work and schooling decisions of children (regardless of who made these choices), yet uncorrelated with the unexplained variation in adult incomes (after controlling for adult labor market conditions, location, family background and other confounding effects). Statistical tests do not reject the validity of these instruments.⁴ A number of previous studies address the consequences of child labor - three of which deserve special mention. In Emerson and Souza (2003), we included an estimate of the impact of child labor on adult earnings in Brazil in a paper that was primarily concerned with the intergenerational transmission of child labor. In that paper we found results that are similar to the OLS results in the current study, but we were unable to control for potentially endogenous variables, however, and the results were, therefore, only suggestive.⁵ Illahi, Orazem and Sedlacek (2001) present results of a related exercise using similar data from

Brazil but where a dichotomous child labor variable is utilized and the impact of having been a child laborer is measured on adult earnings and the incidence of poverty. They find a negative effect of child labor on adult wages, both through the loss of schooling and over and above the loss of schooling, and a higher probability of being impoverished if an individual was a child laborer.

- When a child in addition to getting education, earn his Livelihood, this act of earning a livelihood , is called child labor.
- IT is the employment of children for work in Pakistan leading to mental, physical, moral and social harm to children.
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God has given human beings the boon of wisdom and discretion to think upon the signs of the universe and to draw conclusions. That is the reason why they disclose the hidden facts of it and its structure and have made remarkable

progress in many walks of life. Children are the flowers of heaven. They are the most beautiful and purest creation of God. They are innocent both inwardly and outwardly. No doubt, they are the beauty of this world. Early in the morning when the children put on different kinds of clothes and begin to go to schools for the sake of knowledge, we feel a specific kind of joy through their innocence. But there are also other children, those who cannot go to schools due to financial problems, they only watch others go to schools and can merely wish to seek knowledge. It is due to many hindrances and difficulties; desperate conditions that they face in life. Having been forced to kill their aspirations, dreams and other wishes, they are pressed to earn a living for themselves and for their families. It is also a fact that there are many children who play a key role in sustaining the economically life of their family without which, their families would not be able to make ends meet. These are also part of our society who have forgotten the pleasures of their childhood. When a child in addition to getting education, earns his livelihood, this act of earning a livelihood is called as child Labour. The concept of child Labour got much attention during the 1990s when European countries announced a ban on the goods of the less-developed countries because of child Labour.

The International Labo

- 1- when a child is working during early age
- 2- he overworks or gives over time to Labour
- 3- he works due to the psychologically, socially, and materialistic pressure
- 4- he becomes ready to Labour on a very low pay

Another definition states:

“Child Labour” is generally speaking work for children that harms them or exploits them in some way (physically, mentally, morally or blocking access to education),

United Nations International Children’s Emergency Fund(UNICEF) defines “child” as anyone below the age of 18, and “child Labour” as some type of work performed by children below age 18. (UNICEF)ur Organization (ILO) defines child Labour as:

Child Labour is an important and a serious global issue through which all and sundry countries of the world are directly or indirectly affected, but, it is very common in Latin America, Africa and Asia. According to some, in several Asian countries’ 1/10 manpower consists of child Labour. In India the number of children between the ages of 10-14 has crossed above 44 million, in Pakistan this number is from 8 to 10 million, in Bangladesh 8-12 million, in Brazil 7 million, whereas their number is 12 million in Nigeria . In Pakistan children aged 5-14 are above 40 million. During the last year, the Federal Bureau of Statistics released the results of its survey funded by ILO’s IPEC (International Program on the Elimination of Child Labour). The findings were that 3.8 million children age group of

5-14 years are working in Pakistan out of total 40 million children in this age group; fifty percent of these economically active children are in age group of 5 to 9 years. Even out of these 3.8 million economically active children, 2.7 million were claimed to be working in the agriculture sector. Two million and four hundred thousand (73%) of them were said to be

boys.

During the year 2001 and 2002 the government of Pakistan carried out a series of consultation of tripartite partners and stakeholders (Labour Department, trade unions, employers and NGOs) in all the provinces. The objective was to identify the occupations and the categories of work, which may be considered as hazardous under the provisions of ILO Convention 182. As a result of these deliberations, a national consensus list of occupations and categories of work was identified, which is given below:

1. Nature of occupation-category of work
2. Work inside under ground mines over ground quarries, including blasting and assisting in blasting
3. Work with power driven cutting machinery like saws, shears, and guillotines, (Thrashers, fodder cutting

machines, also marbles)

4. Work with live electrical wires over 50V.

5. All operation related to leather tanning process e.g. soaking, dehairing, liming chrome tanning, delimiting, pickling defleshing, and ink application.

6. Mixing or application of pesticides insecticide/fumigation.

7. Sandblasting and other work involving exposure to free silica.

8. Work with exposure to ALL toxic, explosive and carcinogenic chemicals e.g. asbestos, benzene, ammonia, chlorine, sulphur dioxide, hydrogen sulphide, sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid, nitric acid, caustic soda, phosphorus, benzidine dyes, isocyanides, carbon tetrachloride, carbon disulphide, epoxy, resins, formaldehyde, metal fumes, heavy metals like nickel, mercury chromium, lead, arsenic, beryllium, fiber glass, and

9. Work with exposure to cement dust (cement industry)

10. Work with exposure to coal dust

11. Manufacture and sale of fireworks explosives

12. Work at the sites where Liquid Petroleum Gas (LPG) and Compressed Natural Gas (CNG) are filled in cylinders.

13. Work on glass and metal furnaces

14. Work in the clothe printing, dyeing and finishing sections

15. Work inside sewer pipelines, pits, storage tanks

16. Stone crushing

17. Lifting and carrying of heavy weight specially in transport industry (15b kg and above)

18. Work between 10 pm to 8 am (Hotel Industry)

19. Carpet waving

20. Working 2 meter above the floor

21. All scavenging including hospital waste

22. tobacco process (including Niswar) and Manufacturing

23. Deep fishing (commercial fishing/ sea food and fish processing

24. Sheep casing and wool industry

25. Ship breaking

26. Surgical instrument manufacturing specially in vendors workshop

27. Bangles glass, furnaces

Now we can easily imagine in the light of above mentioned facts and figures how the nation's future namely children are deprived of pleasures of life, ignorance has reduced their abilities of thinking right or differentiating between right and wrong, as well as their life-chances, to their non-access to education. It is true that child Labour is not an isolated phenomenon.

It is an outcome of a multitude of opportunities, high rate of population growth, unemployment, uneven distribution of wealth and resources, outdated social customs and norms and plethora of other factors. According to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) the daily income of 65.5% people of Pakistan is below 2 U.S. dollars a day. According to the Asian Development Bank (ADB) Report, 47 million people in Pakistan are leading lives below the line of poverty, whereas the Social Policy Development Centre (SDPC) Karachi has stated in one of its reports that the ratio of poverty in Pakistan was 33% during 1999 that increased in 2001 and reached 38%. The ratio of poverty in the current year is around 30%.

Consider the point that if 30% of our country's total population is leading life below the poverty-line wherein the people are deprived of basic necessities of life like clothing, shelter, food, education and medication, the children of these people will be forced to become Labourers or workers in order to survive. Another reason of child Labour in Pakistan is that our people don't have the security of social life. There is no aid plan or allowance for children in our country. Class-based education system is another reason for increasing child Labour; villages lack standardized education systems and as a result, child Labour is on increase in rural areas. The government has not put its laws into practice to stop child Labour in our country. Employers after exploiting child Labour, extract a large surplus, whereas child Labour, despite increasing poverty, unemployment and other problems, are pressed to do anything and everything for their livelihood and the survival of their families.

Martin Luther as back far 1524 sent a letter to German Municipalities insisting it was their duty to provide schools, and the duty of parents to educate their children. In Sweden, a royal decree in 1723 instructed parents and guardians to diligently see to it that their children applied themselves to book reading. In Europe, one country after another; Scotland, Prussia (1817), Austria (1869), France, United Kingdom (1880) and Italy made education compulsory. In 1872, Japan became the first non-Western country to make elementary school education compulsory with the declaration by the Meiji Govt.

The present government in Pakistan has made elementary education compulsory. Along with this, the government has distributed free books in primary schools so that parents, who cannot afford their children's school expenses, send their children to schools. The major point is that this decision must be acted upon at all levels. There is strict need to stop child Labour in this country. Awareness must be raised and the attention of parents ought to be diverted to the education of their children. Child Labour Laws should be put into practice strictly. In addition, the educational system of the country-must be reshaped and restructured according to national development goals. The orphans and other deserving children must be helped financially on a prolonged basis. It is also essential to eliminate child Labour from the country, that the political, economical and social system of the country are need to be reshaped and such steps taken that make child Labour in this country a crime. They should bring on the well-being of a lay man, good governance and end to exploitative thinking. If we succeed to act upon these principles, our country can easily get approved by Pakistan, Norway and ILO to eradicate child Labour must be given importance and we hope that our rulers must put this agreement into practice using all means at their disposal. rid of this problem i.e. child Labour. The agreement that has recently been approved by Pakistan, Norway and ILO to eradicate child Labour must be given importance and we hope that our rulers must put this agreement into practice using all means at their disposal.

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WORLD REGIONS	Child labour, 5-14 years (%), 1999-2007*					
	Male		Female		Total	
SUMMARY INDICATORS						
Sub-Saharan Africa	36	n	34	n	35	n
Eastern and Southern Africa	38		33		36	
West and Central Africa	34	n	35	n	35	n
Middle East and North Africa	10		8		9	
South Asia	13		12		13	
East Asia and Pacific	11	**	10	**	10	**
Latin America and Caribbean	11		10		11	
CEE/CIS	5		5		5	
Industrialized countries§	-		-		-	
Developing countries§	17	***	15	***	16	***
Least developed countries§	31		28		30	
World	-		-		-	

Distribution of economically active children in the labour force of Pakistan

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Study methodology included preliminary qualitative research, and cross-sectional sample survey of factory-based and household-based production. The Study estimated that many factories and households were engaged in Pakistan, preceding the survey, of whom (31.5 percent) were children. Almost all (96.3 percent) the children working in industry in Pakistan were working in households. Nearly all children working in Bangle making, iron molding, households and factories (91.7 percent and 94.0 percent, respectively) were living with their parents. While more than half (53.6 percent) of the child workers were girls, amongst the factory-based children, boys made up 78.1 percent of the working children. Pakistan's 1991 Employment of Children Act identifies Carpet weaving, wool cleaning and the wool industry as hazardous occupations. All (100 percent) children working in the industry in Pakistan were engaged in hazardous work based on international standards. In addition, all children (100 percent) reported being exposed to some hazardous agent or process and four-fifths (81.1 percent) showed indications of working excessive hours. There were strong indications that many children working in the industry and their families were in forced/bonded labor, as one-fifth (22.3 percent) of the households were indebted, and two-thirds (68.2 percent) of the indebted households reported having difficulties repaying their debts.

TYPES OF CHILD LABOUR

- INDUSTRIES
- DOMESTIC
- FARM

1)INDUSTRIES CHILD LABOUR

- In a city of Pakistan, Hyderabad children enter work force at the of age 4 or 5 years and they make bangles and bracelets. They make around 12 sets (per set containing 65 bangles) and only gain Rs.40 from all the hard work

2) DOMESTIC CHILD LABOUR

- Household chores include cooking and serving food (chopping vegetables using sharp knives, boiling water, lighting fires, dealing with gas and electricity), fetching and carrying heavy water pots. Washing and ironing clothes, Visiting market and carrying heavy bags

3) FARM CHILD LABOUR

- Children working for wages are classified as being in one of three activities:

REASONS FOR CHILD LABOUR

- POVERTY
- CLASS BASED EDUCATION
- UNEMPLOYMENT
- HIGH RATE OF PAPANULATION GROWTH
- LACK OF OPPURTUNITIES
- GENDER DICRIMINATION

POVERTY

- : Report, 47 million people in Pakistan are leading lines below the line of poverty, whereas the Social Policy Development Centre (SDPC) Karachi has stated in one of its reports that the ratio of poverty in Pakistan was 33% during 1999 that increased in 2001 and reached 38%. The ratio of poverty in the current year is around 30%.

CLASS BAESD EDUCATION

- NEVER EVER A HIGH CLASS PERSON GETS HIS CHILD ADMISSION IN GOVERNMENT INSTITUTES. WHY??

- GENDER DISCRIMINATION

- Amongst the poorest 25% of rural households, a remarkable 19% of girls are in wage work as compared with only 8% of boys; These data indicate that the burden of household poverty is born disproportionately by girls. The gender differential is even more remarkable in the relation of household living standards and school attendance.

Worse effect of child labor

- The commercial sexual exploitation of children is increasing, and organized networks can be found in Latin America, Asia, Africa.
- Child domestic servants also complained about job insecurity and harsh behavior of the employers. About 20% of the children were below average in health physically and psychologically
- The Constitution of Pakistan 1973 prohibits employment of children of 14 years and younger in factories, mines and other hazardous occupations. This provides a protection of children of younger age to enter domestic service as well.
- The Employment of Children Act of 1991 and the Bonded Labor System (Abolition) Act of 1992.
- National Action Plan to Combat Child Labor.

Results of elimination of child labor.

- a *ban* on child work may have deleterious effects in the short run, lowering the wellbeing of both parents and children.
- the *en masse* removal of children from the labor market causes adult wages to be bid up and if the impact on household poverty is large enough.

Conclusion:

Children are the flowers of Heaven They are the most beautiful and purest creation of God. When the children put on different kinds of clothes and begin to go to school for sake of knowledge we feel a kind of joy. But there are also other children those who cannot go to school due to financial problems. This is our duty to support these children and work for to stop child labor in our premises.

- All children have right to get education, love, care equally and properly.

Suggestion

- Make education compulsory
- completion of at least the preliminary education of the child before he or she starts work.
- The orphans and other deserving children must be helped financially on a prolonged basis

REFERENCES

Akabayashi, Hideo and George Psacharopoulos. (1999) "The Trade-off Between Child Labor and Human Capital Formation: A Tanzanian Case Study," *Journal of Development Studies*, v. 35, June.

Baland, Jean-Marie, and James A. Robinson. (2000) "Is Child Labor Inefficient?," *Journal of Political Economy*, Vol. 108, n. 4, pp. 663-679.

Basu, Kaushik. (2002) "A Note on Multiple General Equilibria with Child Labor," *Economics Letters*, Vol. 74, n. 3, pp. 301-308.

Basu, Kaushik. (1999) "Child Labor: Cause, Consequence, and Cure," *Journal of Economic Literature*, Vol. 37, n. 3, pp. 1083-1119.

Basu, Kaushik, and Zafiris Tzannatos. (2003) "The Global Child Labor Problem: What do We Know and What Can we Do?" *World Bank Economic Review*, Vol. 17, n. 2, pp. 147-173.

Basu, Kaushik and Pham Hoang Van. (1998) "The Economics of Child Labor," *American Economic Review*, Vol. 88, n. 3, pp. 412-427.

Becker, Gary S., and Barry R. Chiswick. (1966) "Education and the Distribution of Earnings," *American Economic Review*, Vol. 56, no. 1 / 2, pp. 358-369.

Beegle, Kathleen, Rajeev Dehejia, and Roberta Gatti. (2004) "Why Should We Care About Child Labor? The Returns to Schooling vs. the Returns to Experience in Vietnam"

National Bureau of Economic Research Working Paper No. 10980.

Black, Sandra E., Paul J. Devereux, and Kjell G. Salvanes. (2005) “Why the Apple Doesn’t Fall Far: Understanding Intergenerational Transmission of Human Capital,”

American Economic Review, vol. 95, no. 1, pp. 437-449.

Birdsall, N., and R. H. Sabot, eds. (1996). Opportunity Forgone. Education in Brazil.

IADB: Washington, DC.

Blau, David M. (1999) “The Effect of Income on Child Development,” The Review of Economics and Statistics, Vol. 81, n. 2., pp. 261-276.

Cameron, Stephen V., and Christopher Taber. (2004) “Estimation of Educational Borrowing Constraints Using Returns to Schooling,” Journal of Political Economy, Vol. 112, n. 1, pt. 1, pp. 132-182.

Card, David. (2001) “Estimating the Returns to Schooling: Progress on Some Persistent Econometric Problems,” Econometrica, Vol. 69, pp. 1127-1160.

_____. (1999) “The Causal Effect of Education on Earnings.” The Handbook of Labor Economics, Orley Ashenfelter and David Card, eds. (New York: Elsevier).

_____. (1995a) “Earnings, Schooling and Ability Revisited,” Research in Labor Economics, Vol. 14, n. 1, pp. 23-48.

_____. (1995b) “Using Geographic Variation in College Proximity to Estimate the Return to Schooling.” Aspects of Labour Market Behavior: Essays in Honor of John Vanderkamp, Louis N. Christofides, E. Kenne.